

STUDY OF THE MAIN ASPECTS OF ORGANIZING THE PRACTICE OF STUDENTS IN THE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FIELD

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Abstract

The study of the process of student psychologists' practical training at school is a link between theory and real work, aimed at developing professional identity, adaptation to the school environment and mastering methods of diagnosis, counseling and correction in the educational process. The psychological and pedagogical internship of future psychologists in the education system is an integral part of the core curriculum of higher professional education. The internship of future psychologists in schools fulfills the academic goals and objectives of students' professional development, develops professional knowledge and skills, and facilitates the achievement of professional identity and the acquisition of key competencies.

Keywords: study, basic, aspects, organize, practice, student, psychologist, preparation, development, work, future, school, pupil.

Login.

Over time, the profession of a psychologist becomes a part of its practitioner. Professionals use their skills and knowledge not only in their work with patients but also in everyday life, interacting with loved ones. After all, a psychologist's subject is the human soul, which represents an inexhaustible resource for acquiring essential knowledge. Psychologists help people tap into their inner resources to solve pressing psychological problems.

Educational psychologists use their expertise to promptly redirect current events in the right direction. Children at school face adult challenges: difficult relationships with peers, falling behind in their studies, and feeling misunderstood. If these issues aren't addressed, the child becomes tense and aggressive. In some cases, suicidal tendencies arise. If a psychologist takes appropriate measures, the situation will stabilize.

The goal of training any specialist is to master professional activity in their chosen field. The essence of the psychologist's profession lies in their relationship with others, with their inner world. A psychologist is, first and foremost, a practitioner, but a practitioner possessing a body of professional knowledge and the ability to apply it in specific situations. In today's world, university graduates are required not only to possess academic knowledge but also to possess confident mastery of methods and techniques for solving directly applied and practical problems. The professional work of a psychologist fundamentally differs from many other fields in that the specialist's primary tool is communication.

A psychologist can solve any problem, both theoretical and practical, only through communication. Therefore, pedagogical internships at schools occupy a special place in the training of educational psychologists. The pedagogical internship program at schools is comprehensive, built on the principles of consistency, continuity, and is based on the logic of the educational process. Successful completion of internship assignments at each stage summarizes all previous work and serves as a platform for the student's further acmeological development.

Having acquired a sufficient theoretical foundation and practical experience, fourth-year students, during their teaching internship, learn to construct a socio-psychological profile of an individual and a group, and also master methods of interacting with various categories of participants in the school's educational environment. Fourth-year students are already capable of conducting experimental psychological research on the structure of a group and the place of a specific individual within it, as well as independently planning their interactions with students and analyzing the results. This lays the foundation for developing skills in independent planning and monitoring of their overall activities during their fourth-year internship.

The purpose of industrial practice for psychologists is to consolidate and systematize theoretical knowledge obtained in the study of subject-specific disciplines, and to learn to apply this knowledge in practice in relation to the main types of professional activity.

Research.

A school psychologist's initial work is based on three pillars: studying the regulatory framework, adapting the space, and getting to know the staff. The main goal is to understand the management's needs and create a trusting atmosphere for students and teachers.

School psychologists' internships serve as a link between the theoretical training of future psychologists and their independent practical work in school psychological services. They are conducted in conditions that closely approximate the actual conditions of a secondary school psychologist's future professional work. Working under the supervision of a school psychologist helps create a unified field of activity for the specialist and student interns, facilitating students' direct mastery of a number of key areas and types of professional activity within the school psychological service.

Planning a work schedule is an important aspect of a young psychologist's training. Aspiring school psychologists need to consider how they will allocate time between various types of work—individual and group consultations, diagnostic procedures, educational and

preventive activities. Time should be allocated for documentation, professional development, and self-education.

Internships, both psychological and pedagogical, are an important component of specialist training and enable students to develop practical experience in the implementation of professional functions. The internship is interdisciplinary, connecting with all core disciplines of general professional and subject-specific training [4;5;7].

The psychological and pedagogical internship involves the use of the following organizational forms and methods, including interactive ones, applied during the preparation period and during the internship at school. Forms: orientation and reporting conferences, practical classes in accordance with the internship program, ongoing independent work of students on various types of internship assignments. Practical classes are conducted in the form of seminars and consultations during the preparatory stage of the internship. Practical classes are conducted based on students' self-study according to the internship program. The goal of practical classes is to encourage students to independently search for the necessary scientific and practical information and analyze it in relation to a specific assignment. Methods used: conversations, group discussions, roundtable discussions, case studies, mini-conferences, portfolios, preparation and defense of the internship report. Key techniques used: working with texts, analytical questions, discussion [2;3;7].

During their internship, students must make maximum use of the educational institution's resources to study and integrate advanced psychological practices. To this end, each intern must attend various classes taught by an educational psychologist, experienced psychologists, teachers, and fellow internship participants, as well as participate in extracurricular activities [1;3;6].

In a conversation with the teacher, the intern obtains information about how long the teacher has been working with the class and how well they know it; how the students relate to each other, whether they are interested in class activities; which students are active in the class, and how authoritative are its members; what is the teacher's relationship with the active members; which students actively assist the class teacher; which students' behavior causes concern and why; are there any traditions in the group; does the teacher involve students' parents in their work; what interesting events have been held this academic year, etc.

While attending lessons, the student conducts a psychological and pedagogical analysis, including from the perspective of the organization of individual students' cognitive processes: attention; perception; mnemonic processes; imagination; and thinking. These observations are recorded on a corresponding form and then analyzed. The results of the psychological and pedagogical analysis of the lessons are presented for discussion in a subgroup of classmates, led by the institution's psychologist [1;5;6].

During the internship, the student can provide counseling assistance to students in need. The most common forms of indirect counseling are stand-up ses-

sions or psychological information bulletins. The issues, topic, and target group of the indirect counseling session are agreed upon with the psychologist and school administrator. To identify key issues, a preliminary survey of students and teachers can be conducted, and the topic of the consultation can be selected based on the results.

The intern should be aware that a school psychologist monitors and manages relationships between students, teachers, and parents. They may conduct group sessions with children or, if adults consent, individual consultations. A school psychologist's work encompasses several key areas.

The role of a school psychology intern is to organize effective psychological work with children. During their internship, every young psychologist should contribute to creating a comfortable educational environment, helping students prevent or resolve conflicts, and avoid psychological trauma.

During their internships, future school psychologists must learn how to effectively interact with teachers using practical psychological tools and methods that can also be used when working with parents. They conduct seminars and consultations with school students, especially high school students, and learn to help teachers maintain a comfortable emotional environment in the classroom and build rapport with each student. Psychology trainees also work with school psychologists to resolve conflicts between teachers and parents.

Conclusion.

A school psychologist's work is aimed at maintaining children's mental health, supporting their adaptation, overcoming learning difficulties, and resolving conflicts. They help students, teachers, and parents interact more harmoniously, while remaining an independent, non-judgmental figure. Therefore, during their internship, students must carefully study all these aspects for their future work.

Internships are a mandatory component of core professional educational programs in higher education and represent a type of learning activity directly focused on the professional and practical training of students, their acquisition of necessary practical knowledge, skills, and competencies in their field of study, and the development of relevant competencies in their field of study. The organization of internships at all stages is aimed at ensuring the continuity and consistency of students' acquisition of professional skills in accordance with the requirements for the graduate's level of preparation.

The essence of the work of a student school psychologist internship is to learn to solve various problems related to academic performance, behavior, personal growth, and relationships in the school environment.

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